

THE IMPACT OF NATIONAL IDEA AND IDEOLOGY ON SOCIAL CONSCIOUSNESS IN RENEWED UZBEKISTAN

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In the management of new Uzbekistan, issues such as the moral and moral factors of national idea and ideological criteria, the important criteria of the Society for the renewal of the idea, the social and spiritual development of the National idea and national problems have been thoroughly analyzed. Each nation will have its own unique, national idea, historically formed and found gloss. With the formation of any nation, its specific national idea is also formed. Therefore, the literal meaning of the concept of national idea is one of the highest values historically enriched by freedom, peace, humanity, kindness, loyalty to the motherland, selflessness, friendship and tolerance. After all, the love brought from Syria and Iraq in 2021 year is 1,2,3,4,5-stage operations, a practical proof of the national ideological essence.

The strategy of the new Uzbekistan is the manifestation of the National idea as a lakomativ of economic –national base in human capital and culture, the legal basis of which is not just a phenomenon of despondency-desire or subjectivity, but also an object of necessity, having a fundamental historical basis, fully responding to the national interests of the nation, which dictates the socio-economic.

Russian politician scientist K.S.Gadzhiev: "relatively high countries of the world political space define their national interests in Real political reality, depending on their ideological, moral and other views as a secondary task», there is a certain truth in his writing. As in the pamphlet, it is said that with the change in interests, the relationship of the structures of society, as well as their regulatory prints, means of propaganda and requirements, is also improving. During the years of independence, the first president of Uzbekistan I.A.Karimov's recommendations on popularization and establishment of active participation of citizens in social life in the socio-political, economic liberalization and radical renewal of society, socio-economic revision and reform of the country, were manifested as the main driving force of the reforms of the period of independence.

By the present time, the priority directions associated with the restoration of the legal system in our state, the construction of civil society, and the principle of "strategy of development from the strategy of action" have been set forward-looking tasks. In this sense, the law is this, this is a mutual agreement between citizens. On the basis of the National idea, of course, lies the rule of law. The system of recording, formalizing, controlling the implementation and implementation of this agreement, as well as the activities of public control, will be understandable to all, will determine the level of community integrity, the role of the state in the world community and the level of national commitment.

Based on this, it has become one of the directions and tasks of scientific research of the present day, further enriching it, revealing in depth the vital, socio-ideological essence of the National idea and ideology formed before in our society. In the current period, which is developing rapidly, at the level of modern thinking, efforts to conduct socio-economic reforms in the country and, as a result, to radically change the standard of living of people, the life-giving ideas of the national ideology and the increase of their influence are of urgent importance.

The existence of Uzbekistan among the 10 developing countries of the world as a result of socio-economic reforms, uniform, advanced experience and technologies in the development of society is a clear proof of this.

The formation and decision - making of a strong civil society in Uzbekistan is directly related to its fate, the participation of citizens in the socio-political arena. The participation of citizens is an ideological goal, the realization of such goals as equality in their minds, the embodiment and strengthening of noble values.

Our President Sh.M. The consistent reforms carried out by Mirziyoev are an indicator of the integration of the cultural, religious, scientific and practical significance of the National idea, which is considered to be the basis of life in the country in terms of achieving democratic perfection. On this path, on the scale of the state, the issue of national ideological outlook, which expresses the final results of the actions carried out by the government, political parties, public organizations, in the context of the continuity of socio-political relations and their improvement, in the conduct of behato, object and systematic implementation, there is no doubt that it has a significant place.

New Uzbekistan relies on a modernized economy. And economic facts and examples, which are considered its basis, mean that the core of the National idea is the perfect economy. The formation and implementation of Democratic stages in Uzbekistan also makes it possible to compare positive approaches and identify the main directions of modernization processes.

The annual population growth in Uzbekistan is 1.2-1.5 million.it makes up the person. Aksi do this while in developed European countries. According to the sociologists ' calculations, the population of Uzbekistan is 45 per capita mln.ga it is predicted that the growth rate will fall slightly when reached. In this regard, in order to solve the problems of the population in the state, to meet the need for housing for the purpose of improving the well-being of the population and to carry out a number of positive works by our government in this regard, the provision of housing by subsidies, sponsors and the relevant organization, enterprises and institutions for In turn, the rapid and systematic organization of activities in achieving such noble goals, achieving labor efficiency, determines the essence and priority direction of our national –ideological reforms.

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